

ISic2868

I.Sicily inscription 2868

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12302

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334811

1. Κορνηλί-
2. ου Κτη-
3. στου
4. Ἔ[ρ]μος.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645262

PHI 334811

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1381.99

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 703

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprieta Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.99 pl.133

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